

MATHEMATICAL SCIENCES

APPLICATION OF GEOMETRIC METHODS TO SOLVE SOME ALGEBRAIC PROBLEMS

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Abstract

Algebraic methods are commonly used to solve geometric problems, and in many cases, they prove to be more practical than geometric methods. However, for certain algebraic problems that are challenging to solve algebraically, geometric methods can offer simpler solutions. We will demonstrate this through the resolution of specific problems.

Keywords: geometric methods, the trapezoid, arithmetic mean.

The work is dedicated to the use of geometric methods in solving algebraic problems. The distinctive feature of the geometric method, which stems from visual representations, creates favorable opportunities for developing professionally significant qualities in students, such as spatial imagination and logical thinking. As academician A.D. Alexandrov (1980) noted, "The geometric method is nothing more than living imagination, where one finds guidance for a logically conducted solution".

As demonstrated by practice and the results of our research, geometric representations and methods play a significant role in solving algebraic word problems. The primary goal of solving these problems is to introduce students to mathematical modeling and develop their ability to construct and analyze basic mathematical models. To do so, you have to diversify the process of teaching, to improve the methods of teaching, to start using new approaches for some problems. Let us note

works (Aliyev et al., 2025; Aliyev et al., 2024; Aliyev et al., 2023; Aliyev et al., 2022; Aliyev et al., 2021; Aliyev et al., 2020; Aleksandrov, 1980), which are devoted to the study of these issues.

In the process of solving certain algebraic problems, those that are difficult to solve using algebraic methods can be easily solved with geometric methods. Let us explain this through the solution of specific problems.

First, let us prove inequality

$$\sqrt{ab} \leq \frac{a+b}{2} \quad (1)$$

for any numbers $a > 0$ and $b > 0$ using a geometric method. Let the point O be the center of the circumcircle of the right triangle ABC .

Figure 1. (The triangle ABC inscribed in a circle)

Drop a perpendicular AH from point A to the side BC , and assume that $BH = a$, $HC = b$. Then we have $AO = BO = OC = \frac{a+b}{2}$. On the other side $AH = \sqrt{ab}$, because $AH^2 = BH \cdot HC$.

It is easy to see that $|AH| \leq |AO|$ and from here, we deduce the validity of inequality (1).

Let us prove inequality (1) using another geometric method. Let in the rectangle $ABCD$ $AB = a$, $BC = b$. Let the point of intersection of the bisector of angle A and the extension of side BC be denoted by M .

Figure 2. (The segment AM is the angle bisector of the rectangle $ACBD$)

Since the triangles ADN and AMB are isosceles, we have $DN = b$ and $BM = a$, respectively. It is clear that

$$S_{ABCD} \leq S_{ADN} + S_{AMB}.$$

From this we get

$$a \cdot b \leq \frac{1}{2}b \cdot b + \frac{1}{2}a \cdot a \Rightarrow ab \leq \frac{a^2 + b^2}{2}.$$

In the last inequality, writing $a = \sqrt{x}$, $b = \sqrt{y}$, we obtain inequality (1):

$$\sqrt{xy} \leq \frac{x+y}{2}.$$

Now, let us prove using a geometric method that the harmonic mean for any $a > 0$ and $b > 0$ is not greater than the arithmetic mean.

$$\frac{2}{\frac{1}{a} + \frac{1}{b}} \leq \frac{a+b}{2},$$

$$\frac{2ab}{a+b} \leq \frac{a+b}{2}. \tag{2}$$

To do this, let us take the trapezoid $ABCD$ with bases $AB = a$ and $CD = b$. Draw the line segment MN from the intersection point K of the diagonals AC and BD of the trapezoid, parallel to the bases. Let's designate $MK = x$. It is easy to show that $KN = MK = x$.

Figure 3. (The line segment MN , drawn from the point K , the intersection of the diagonals AC and BD of the trapezoid $ABCD$, is parallel to the bases)

From the similarity of triangles DKC and BKA , it follows that

$$\frac{b}{a} = \frac{KC}{AK}. \tag{3}$$

But from the similarity of triangles AMK and ADC , we have

$$\frac{AC}{AK} = \frac{b}{x}.$$

Consider that $AC = AK + KC$ and the relation (3) given above:

$$\frac{AK + KC}{AK} = \frac{b}{x} \Rightarrow 1 + \frac{KC}{AK} = \frac{b}{x} \Rightarrow 1 + \frac{b}{a} = \frac{b}{x} \Rightarrow$$

$$x = \frac{ab}{a+b} \Rightarrow MN = \frac{2ab}{a+b}.$$

It is clear that the line MN is closer to DC than to AB , meaning the segment MN is not greater than the midline of the trapezoid:

$$\frac{2ab}{a+b} \leq \frac{a+b}{2}.$$

Relation (2) has been proven.

Finally, using geometric methods, let us prove that the arithmetic mean of two numbers is not greater than their quadratic mean, i.e.,

$$\frac{a+b}{2} \leq \sqrt{\frac{a^2 + b^2}{2}}. \tag{4}$$

In the trapezoid $ABCD$ with bases $AB = a$ and $CD = b$, draw a line segment $EF = x$ parallel to the bases such that the area of the trapezoid is divided into two equal parts.

Figure 4. (The line segment EF dividing the area of the trapezoid $ABCD$ into two equal parts)

Draw the line segment KM from point F , parallel to AD . If we denote the height of the trapezoid $EFCD$ by h_1 and the height of the trapezoid $ABFE$ by h_2 , then from the equality of areas it follows that:

$$\frac{b+x}{2} \cdot h_1 = \frac{a+x}{2} \cdot h_2 \Rightarrow \frac{h_1}{h_2} = \frac{a+x}{b+x} \quad (5)$$

On the other side, from the similarity of triangles CKF and BMF , we have

$$\frac{h_1}{h_2} = \frac{x-b}{a-x}$$

Let us consider this in (5):

$$\frac{a+x}{b+x} = \frac{x-b}{a-x} \Rightarrow x = \sqrt{\frac{a^2 + b^2}{2}}$$

Since $a > b$, from the equality of areas, it follows that the segment $EF = x$ is closer to AB than to DC , meaning the segment EF is located between the base AB and the midline of the trapezoid, and thus, the validity of equality (4) follows.

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